

The Use of Joint Coordinates to Monitor Patients in a Movement-Based Interaction System

Juan E. Garrido
Albacete Research Institute of
Informatics
University of Castilla-La Mancha
Albacete, Spain
juanenrique.garrido@uclm.es

Victor M. R. Penichet,
Maria Dolores Lozano
Computer Systems Department
University of Castilla-La Mancha
Albacete, Spain
{victor.penichet,
maria.lozano}@uclm.es

Alberto Mora Plata,
Jose A. F. Valls
Albacete Research Institute of
Informatics
University of Castilla-La Mancha
Albacete, Spain
albermorap@gmail.com,
josea.fernandez@uclm.es

ABSTRACT

Movement-based interaction has brought about new possibilities in healthcare environments. Concretely, rehabilitation therapies represent an adequate domain in which this kind of systems can produce significant benefits. In this context, the authors have developed SIVIRE, a movement-based interaction system whose main contributions are a virtual online editor of exercises with the capacity to adapt the rehabilitation to the patients' conditions and evolution. During the development process, we have considered some aspects regarding the monitoring process to improve the quality and accuracy of the system, such as monitoring the patient's postures, which is a critical procedure in order to properly correct and guide them. Specifically, this paper presents a descriptive study of three methods that address the monitoring process in a different way: the first using joint coordinates, the second based on bones coordinates and the last using the angles generated by the bones. Following the analysis of these three different mechanisms, the authors discuss the reason to identify the use of joint coordinates as the best technique to monitor patients in this kind of movement-based interaction systems. Such technique has been applied in the development of SIVIRE. Finally, we present the results of the evaluation of the system implemented with this monitoring mechanism. The outcomes prove that SIVIRE offers a reliable and useful tool to support rehabilitation therapies, both for patients and physiotherapists.

CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing -> Interaction design.**

Keywords

Rehabilitation, healthcare, movement-based interaction, monitoring

1. INTRODUCTION

Technology evolution supports the capability to work with movement interaction when seeking improvements in different domains. The possibility to interact in a natural way, through the human body, allows users to utilize richer interactions than traditional ones (e.g. based on keyboard and mouse). This generates an interesting and emerging research field named Natural User Interfaces (NUI). The tendency in the development of applications,

and more specifically in the development of user interfaces, is to make them invisible. In a Natural User Interface (NUI), the user can directly interact with the application in an intuitive way. Their movements are close or even equal to the movements they would use in a non-computational context. Such an interaction style reduces the mental workload a user needs to interact with the application and provides them with a quick and soft transition to a proper use of the application.

NUIs are usually designed according to some principles [3]. *Performance aesthetics*, i.e. NUI experiences focus on the joy of doing. *Direct Manipulation* enables users to interact directly with information objects. Fewer options can be found with interaction *scaffolding*, a strong cue or guide that sets users' expectations by giving them an indication of how the interaction will unfold. NUIs are responsive to the environment (*contextual environment*) and suggest what the next interaction should be. The UI elements of NUIs not only look real, but we also perceive them to be *super real* as their character can change in a way that is almost magical. NUIs enable opportunities for users to engage and interact with other users of the system's interface (*social interaction*). NUIs represent information as objects (*spatial relationships*). Lastly, NUI interactions make the user feel seamless because the interactions are direct; there are fewer barriers between the user and the information than in traditional GUIs.

In recent years, different devices which recognises users' movements have appeared and have brought about the possibility of introducing these new ways of interaction. The user feels more comfortable with the applications since their interactions are much more natural than before. There is no need to use an artificial device such as a mouse, a keyboard, or any other specialized input device, as users only need their own body to interact with the software application. The user performs tasks as in the real world because these devices can identify and process their movements. Movement-based interaction gives the user the feeling of being understood by the system. Just by moving, or making gestures, the user starts a communication with the application which is by far more natural if properly implemented.

Wearables such as the Myo armband¹ are gesture-control and motion-control devices that let you take control of your phone or computer. These wearables usually include motion sensors (three-

¹ Myo armband. Thalmic Labs Inc. <https://www.myo.com/>

axis gyroscope and three-axis accelerometer), and three-axis magnetometer. Other devices are used out of the body of the user. Leap motion², for instance, senses how the user moves their hands and fingers by means of a tracking peripheral in the distance. This kind of hardware usually relies on different types of cameras (infrared IR, RGB), depth sensors and/or microphone arrays.

Movement-based interaction devices offer possibilities to users that did not exist some years ago. Nowadays, they can interact with mechanisms near to their daily needs and physical capabilities. The result is a wide range of areas of interest which range from game industry or interactive art to medicine. Section 2 will present some current systems which rely on the aforementioned types of devices, NUI and Healthcare (mainly rehabilitation).

The authors have focused their efforts on applying movement interaction in Healthcare environments. The main objective has been to improve complex conditions of medical staff and patients [2]. Firstly, we have developed a system, named KFF System [3], to automatically detect falls and fainting. The system is conceived for residential care homes. The objective is to detect anomalous situations that occur in unattended locations. The reason is to be able to ensure that all residents are visualized by one employee, at least. Figure 1 shows an example carried out in a room. In this case, it is assumed that a patient is having a rest after lunch. KFF system automatically detects the situation. If the patient spends too much time in this posture, the system starts an alert protocol. As a result, the employee in charge of alerts receives a video signal of what is happening and then acts accordingly. The system could send an audio signal to the resident to confirm a correct state. In this case, however, the system avoids any interaction with the resident as the time is considered a rest hour.

Figure 1. Example of the automatic process carried out by KFF System

KFF System helped authors to further study movement interaction through Kinect. Its development boosted the need to investigate and work within the existing capabilities. Consequently, a second system, named SIVIRE, was developed with the aim to improve rehabilitation processes based on postures repetition remotely [2]. On the one hand, the system facilitates the tasks of the rehabilitation staff. The user can create a customizable table of exercises through a web application with a 3D editor manually or with their own body, using Kinect. On the other hand, the patient can perform the exercises through the web application. The system guides, corrects and assists the patient during the process. To that end, the user interacts with the system through Kinect, using their body.

The user can carry out the exercises in any location. The patient can go through the rehabilitation process wherever they want. Therefore, the system allows patients to continue their daily life.

The implication of the medical staff, however, is not bypassed. Their role is important as they have to define and control the evolution of the process. The system is not a substitute, it is a support tool. The rehabilitation staff can obtain a detailed follow-up of the patient evolution during the rehabilitation therapy. This is thanks to the precision of Kinect during the exercises when detecting postures. In addition, the need of the therapist to be physically present is not required. The system eliminates the dependence between the completion of the exercise and the control made by medical staff, which results in time saving.

In the case of KFF System, it is based on the use of patterns that represent known postures. The system compares, as part of a complex parametric study, the current detected posture with previously defined ones. KFF System only requires the detection of a pattern to activate the alert protocol. However, patterns are not enough during the development of the rehabilitation system.

The automatic and constant monitoring carried out on a rehabilitation exercise is a requirement and affects the way it is checked. The patients have different movement capabilities, thus, it is important to consider specific difficulty levels per each exercise posture. Each level defines an error threshold that will be used to check each posture. This fact raises the problem of determining the adequate monitoring technique to apply. Therefore, it leads to think about several possibilities at the time of dealing with the problem of identifying a concrete posture: (1) to use joint coordinates; (2) to check bones coordinates; or (3) to use the angles that are generated by the implied bones to check the position. In some applications, monitoring accuracy is variable depending on the exercise and on the evolution of the patient. These applications need a proper method to identify, process and check the parts of the human body. Sometimes it is not possible to use just the basic algorithms. The paper aims to describe the different monitoring techniques in order to analyse them. This study and the subsequent evaluation show their strengths and weaknesses, which will determine the most adequate method to be applied in SIVIRE. Hopefully these outcomes will be able to work in other approaches based on monitoring patients in their rehabilitation processes. We do not tackle other issues regarding monitoring. Usability, context setting, or fault tolerance, among others, are some key factors to study. However, in this paper we particularly focus on skeleton detection.

The organization of the paper is as follows: Section 2 presents existing rehabilitation systems based on movement interaction, including the solution developed by the authors. Section 3 describes the techniques studied address with the monitoring process in rehabilitation exercises. Section 4 discusses about which is the most adequate option. Finally, Section 5 presents conclusions and future work.

2. REHABILITATION SYSTEMS BASED ON MOVEMENT INTERACTION

Movement-based interaction appears to be a successful component in casual environments (e.g. video games) through readily available devices. Such conditions have raised great interest regarding their application in medical settings. Specifically, rehabilitation processes with physical exercises is one of the main areas in which the research community has found a suitable environment to apply these techniques.

² Leap Motion. Leap Motion Inc. <https://www.leapmotion.com/>

A key feature of movement-based interaction is to support the system to be controlled by natural movements such as hand gestures or postures. In addition, this mechanism offers the possibility to analyse each existing situation and react accordingly [10]. For instance, posture detection and identification represent valuable elements to determine corrections, alert reactions, etc. This is the core of many existing works focused on rehabilitation processes that have appeared within the aforementioned research field.

The first noteworthy example is VirtualRehab [11], a new system for physical rehabilitation using movement-based interaction provided by Kinect. The system allows the monitoring and tracking of patients from any location. The main objective of VirtualRehab is to offer patients an enjoyable way of completing complex rehabilitation processes at home. To this end, the equipment required comprises a personal computer, Kinect for Windows and a screen. Additionally, VirtualRehab contains a manager that enables medical staff to plan, monitor and review each patient's progress. The system focuses on specific pathologies: acquired brain damage, neuromuscular diseases, neurodegenerative diseases and reduced mobility in older adults. To treat these pathologies, VirtualRehab places patients in a virtual world in which they can work with nine games to perform specific movements in order to improve. These games make it possible to work with the affected parts of the body and physical symptoms, particularly in loss of motor ability, movement and posture disorder, and balance and coordination disorder.

SeeMe [9] is another major study on rehabilitation, though in this case, it corresponds to the assessment and treatment of unilateral spatial neglect. This project represents another system for rehabilitation that creates a virtual reality environment without the requirement of head-mounted displays or specialized equipment. SeeMe is a projected video capture of a virtual story in which the patient is embedded through their image. A representation of the patient is generated by capturing the patient performing the activities through a camera and using specific algorithms for movement and position recognition and analysis. The participants should stand or sit in a specific area, viewing a monitor in which their virtual representation is shown during the exercises inside the virtual world. For example, patients can be embedded in a game in which they are touching virtual balls. Therefore, the participants can see themselves in a virtual story using trunk and limb movements. Additionally, the medical staff is able to change parameters of the virtual game (based on system indications and staff perceptions) during the rehabilitation procedure in order to adapt exercises and features according to patient progress and needs. In this way, SeeMe generates a set-up where patients and medical staff are together while the patient is working at the medical centre.

The Reflexion Rehabilitation Measure Tool (RMT) [14] is a Kinect-based system that allows the patient to perform rehabilitation exercises at home. The system gathers patient information, which is sent to the specialists. They may then analyse it and change the therapy if needed. Interactive feedback is provided to the patient. In this way, they get entertainment while they properly perform the exercises. An assistant character guides the patient in their performance, and gives them some clues about how to proceed. A coloured shadow represents the patient instead of their real image.

KinetiSense [11] represents an alternative without replacing the patient by an avatar. The system shows the monitoring process on the own patient. In this case, the capabilities offered are the action

of measuring, recording and analysing the patient's movements and postures. Furthermore, the system informs about the progress, thus being a useful tool for medical staff who are able to control evolutions related to specific treatments.

The Virtual Exercise Rehabilitation Assistant (VERA) is a tele-rehabilitation application to guide a patient through a home exercise program without direct supervision [12]. Working on lower extremity exercises and using an on-screen avatar, VERA automatically tracks patients' exercise repetitions and provides real-time corrections criteria. Results are stored to be reviewed by patients and medical staff.

Lastly, another remarkable system for physical rehabilitation is RespondWell [13]. The application offers support for medical staff in terms of monitoring, telehealth and data management. Patients find in RespondWell a tool with which they increase their motivation during the process by providing users with a fun experience.

The authors have developed an alternative system, named SIVIRE. The system is a comprehensive solution for editing, monitoring and guiding exercises of physical rehabilitation. It is a solution to avoid daily displacements of patients or medical staff. SIVIRE presents novel features in comparison to related works, however two aspects can be remarked. The system can customize the exercises to the patient's conditions but also, the exercises can be adapted and personalized according to the patient's evolution. In the following subsection, the system foundations are introduced.

Figure 2. Modular architecture of SIVIRE

2.1 SIVIRE: System to Improve Rehabilitation Processes

SIVIRE is both a system to assist a patient in their process of rehabilitation, and a complete editor of exercises which allows the physiotherapist to design and create tables of exercises. The desktop application drives the user in the correct performance of their daily and repetitive exercises. Through different multimodal guides users receive practical tips in every step for them to know what to do next. If there is any improper execution, the patient is warned and advised in various ways (auditory, visual, etc.). Additionally, the physiotherapist designs the set of exercises through a Web application. The exercises are customized according to the problem to be addressed by the user. Moreover, the physiotherapist can consider the evolution and the particularities of each user personalizing the exercises from the beginning and during the treatment. The information about every movement of the user in the process of their rehabilitation is stored and shown to the physiotherapist for further conscientious study of the patient.

Patients do not need to wear any invasive peripheral as every movement is captured in the distance. The patients feel comfortable since the system is minimally invasive. They can naturally move similarly as they would do in a traditional rehabilitation process. However, they are still monitored and guided. In fact, they are continuously monitored and guided in real time.

SIVIRE was designed in a modular way according to its main functionality (see Figure 2). It is composed of four interrelated modules, namely *virtual edition of exercises module (EVITE)*, *monitoring and guiding module (REHABILITA)*, *statistics module* and *home support module*.

Virtual edition of exercises module (EVITE). This module provides medical staff with an editor to create and customize tables and

exercises. This element appears to be a novel feature in comparison to related works. The result is the capacity to offer versatility and a high level of customization and personalization when designing the different types of rehabilitation exercises according to the patient's conditions and evolution.

The editor provides the physiotherapist with the possibility of designing exercises by means of two options: (1) *manual interaction* in which the user interacts directly with the tool; (2) *through movement-based interaction* offered by Kinect. The interaction acts on a 3D skeleton representing a person with selectable and movable points (Figure 3-C). The result is an easy way to define postures to be repeated in the exercises.

The main part of the working environment of EVITE is the virtual space. This simulates a room, whose dimensions match with the vision field of Kinect, that contains a 3D skeleton representing a person with selectable and movable points (Figure 3-C). The scenario is 3D what allows its rotation among three dimensions (x, y, and z). Therefore, the user can establish a customizable view of the skeleton in order to generate an adequate posture. The editor contains different elements associated to several functionalities and actions. To support the physiotherapist with tools and actions to accelerate the design, the editor has a tool bar (Figure 3-B) with different icons to redo/undo, activate movement-interaction, change views, insert specific postures, etc. As the editor works with three axes (x, y, z), the user can move the 3D environment around them with three sliders (Figure 3-D). Finally, the physiotherapist can select basic postures (Figure 3-A) and determine properties (Figure 3-E). These properties represent a remarkable feature of the editor since it supports the customization of each exercise by modifying the parameters provided: selection of implied joints, which joint should be checked or ignored, difficulty levels, transitions, messages, etc.

Figure 3. 3D-Virtual Editor of SIVIRE

The implementation of the virtual Web editor relies on WebGL (Web Graphics Library). WebGL [8] is a cross-platform, royalty-free web standard for a low-level 3D graphics API based on OpenGL ES 2.0, exposed through the HTML5 Canvas element as Document Object Model interfaces. It is important to notice that this JavaScript API renders 3D graphics within any compatible Web browser without the use of plug-ins. Therefore, the large majority of users would be able to design exercises through this module through any computer with Internet connection and a Web browser. There is no need to install any other complex software and the design can be modified wherever and whenever.

Monitoring and guiding module. This module analyses and helps the patient during the rehabilitation exercises previously defined by the physiotherapist through the virtual editor. The patient checks their movements in real time with visual (see Figure 4) and auditory feedback, being aware of corrections and next steps.

The approach we present in this paper to properly monitor patients through movement based interaction mainly concerns this module. The following section presents a more in-depth description of the monitoring module as well as the approach itself.

Statistics module. The physiotherapist usually takes notes of the evolution of a patient to study their improvements as well as to know what parts of the exercise should be modified if something goes wrong. This is what they do in a traditional process. We have implemented this module to enhance this part of the therapy, which is the most important one since the physiotherapist is absolutely aware of any movement, improvement or difficulty in the evolution of the patient. The module records any message and difficulty associated to postures, time and exercise. All the information stored is processed and the module provide the physiotherapist with some statistics of the performance of the rehabilitation exercises. Thus,

the physiotherapist decides how to modify the exercise modifying thresholds in the joints, independently, to make that part easier or more difficult to perform. The progress of the patient is gradually personalized through such modifications in the exercises.

Home support module. The traditional rehabilitation process requires the user to perform the same exercises many times every day for weeks or even months. Patients do not usually live close to the rehabilitation centre. They sometimes require ambulance transport, which is uncomfortable, tiring and expensive. The monitoring system we present is thought to be used anywhere. At first, the physiotherapist watches the progress of the patient. At a certain point, the professional may decide that the patient is ready to perform the exercises by themselves, still watched, though provides just with the support of the monitoring system at home. The REHABILITA module provides the patient with a login system and the interface to select the assigned table of exercises. The selection of the exercises is designed by the physiotherapist through the EVITE module. It is individually assigned to each patient to follow their evolution. The module also shows the patient some statistics and adjustments. In addition, the user can interact with the system through movement, voice and traditional interaction.

SIVIRE contains many aspects to work on. One of them is the monitoring process, which is the core of the REHABILITA module. The procedure to accurately monitor the user represents a key issue to solve during the development. Once the general idea of the system and the main modules have been described, the following section will focus on the monitoring system, and more specifically in the key decisions we reached to provide accuracy in the matching between the postures the patient should perform and the movements they really do.

Figure 4. Visual appearance of the application for home rehabilitation support

3. MONITORING OF PATIENT'S POSTURES THROUGH MOVEMENT INTERACTION

The usefulness of rehabilitation exercises is highly dependent on the monitoring process. The way patients are analysed during the rehabilitation process to be guided, helped and encouraged, is essential. In this sense, it is important to compare the actual posture of the patient through their skeleton with the expected one. Based on this, the authors have been working with rehabilitation therapies defined as exercises consisting of sequence of postures to be repeated. The main step has been to define the adequate way to perform the monitoring process using movement-based interaction. Considering the possibilities of Kinect, we identified and analysed three different options.

Kinect detects the skeleton of the user and offers a representation composed of bones and joints. These elements provide different alternatives when monitoring postures and the transitions between them. The authors analysed techniques based on: (1) joint coordinates; (2) bone coordinates; and (3) angle between bones. Next, we describe each technique in order to know what involves and then, be able to determine the most adequate for the monitoring process. Firstly, we describe the monitoring system for a better understanding of the process.

3.1 Description of the monitoring system

As previously mentioned, the monitoring module analyses and helps the patient during the rehabilitation exercises defined by the physiotherapist through the virtual editor. The patient may check their movements in real time with visual (see Figure 4) and auditory feedback, being aware of corrections and next steps.

The monitoring module works with exercises composed of three elements: *postures*, *transitions* between postures and *messages*. The *posture* is the key component of an exercise as an exercise is composed of a set of postures. The posture defines the pose the patient should match in every step of an exercise. *Transitions* are the movements the patient performs to get a posture from a previous one. This intermediate step ensures that the exercise can be performed properly; otherwise the patient could move from one posture to the next without considering the correct transition, which would not guarantee doing the exercise in an appropriate manner. Lastly, the *messages* are visual elements shown when monitoring the patient to guide the user in the performance of the exercise, and also to correct them when something is wrong. Thus, we distinguish between *guiding messages* and *error messages*. Guiding messages indicate the patient how to reach the current posture. The physiotherapist includes as many guiding messages as they consider appropriate for better understanding of this process. Some examples of guiding messages are: "lower the right arm", "go one step forward", "sit down on the chair". Only when a patient reaches a posture, error messages are shown if the posture is not the correct one. This kind of messages still tries to guide the user. The main difference with the guiding messages is that they do not show what to do to reach a proper posture, rather what the patient is doing incorrectly in their process to reach the posture. In this sense, the patient is aware of what is exactly the problem to succeed in the current step. Some examples of error messages are: "place your right leg properly" and "keep your neck straight".

The user interface is a key element in the monitoring module. The feedback the user receives is a key factor for proper performance of the exercises. As already mentioned, the user receives auditory and

visual feedback. Visual feedback is provided to the patient in various manners (Figure 4):

- *Messages panel*. Textual messages are shown on top of the user interface;
- *Progress bar*. They are information-rich elements. Summarizing, we could say that they allow patients to be aware of the evolution of the exercise at any time. They provide the progress of the current posture, the number of postures to be performed and the evolution of the complete exercise (number of repetitions);
- *Balance*. Patient balance is a key factor in certain exercises. It could be extremely important in the entire exercise or just in particular points. This element offers feedback about the balance of the patient. It could even inform them about towards where they are bending. This information prevents falls and controls straight postures. If the inclination of the patient is too much to maintain balance, a red arrow appears to reinforce the message;
- *Guide skeleton*. The guide skeleton is in fact a couple of overlapped skeletons. One represents the posture to be reached and the other the current patient's posture. The objective is to visually show possible errors. On the patient-posture skeleton, some colours appear to show if the joints are where they should be (Figure 5-Correction phase) and if the posture was properly reached (Figure 5-Final Verification).

Patients also receive voice information. They can pay attention to the visual feedback, but still they receive auditory information about what to do to reach the proper posture as well as information about possible errors in that process. Voice guiding messages are produced just once. If an error is detected in the process of reaching a posture, a voice error message is given after a certain time. It is not precisely when detected, but after a certain period of time. We do not want to bother the patient excessively, as they need time to react. If the problem continues, the voice error message is given once again.

Figure 5. Monitoring and guiding of REHABILITA module

The monitoring process is divided into four steps because of the feedback needs (see Figure 5). Each step implies specific verifications with its own information to show. The steps are: (1)

verification of transitions between postures; (2) guide to help patients reach the final posture; (3) correction of final posture; (4) final verification to ensure the maintenance of the final posture. The patient is not aware of these steps, as they only perceive the corresponding information.

3.2 Monitoring Based on Joint Coordinates

This monitoring technique verifies if each joint is in the adequate position. The procedure takes as reference the origin of coordinates used by Kinect (see Figure 6) and consists of checking if the absolute coordinates of the patient joints match with those of the physiotherapist designed (using the virtual editor, see Figure 3).

Figure 6. Coordinates axes used by Kinect

In this case, error thresholds are essential when a patient is performing rehabilitation exercises. The monitoring requires an adaptive verification without the need to find points whose coordinates are totally equal to the expected ones, nonetheless, they should be within a defined range.

As the working space is three-dimensional, each joint threshold is represented by a sphere whose centre and radius defines the joint and threshold value (see Figure 7-a), respectively. The procedure, based on joint coordinates, allows a patient's joint to be correctly positioned if the point representing it is inside the sphere which defines the joint of the designed posture by the physiotherapist. Figure 7-b represents an example in which a patient performs a posture correctly with the elbow because the threshold is respected.

Figure 7. a) Representation of a threshold as a sphere; b) elbow checking through spheres

The mechanism to offer the aforementioned monitoring technique corresponds to the following formula:

$$(x_U + x_C) + (y_U + y_C) + (z_U + z_C) \leq r^2$$

The formula checks if a specific point named U (patient's skeleton point) is within the sphere with centre C (physiotherapist's skeleton point) and radius r (error threshold).

This technique helps to check if a joint is in a concrete position but also, it allows checking two or more joints and, consequently, different bones. In this case, the verification of a bone implies to check each of its joints and analyse them in the same way.

3.2.1 Escalation and Translation

The dependence between the postures to be checked, the user's height and their spatial position is a problem when monitoring through absolute coordinates of the joint offered by Kinect. This inconvenience is solved with specific three-dimensional geometric transformations: *escalation* and *translation*.

The transformation results in an adjustment of the physiotherapist's skeleton to the patient's one by means of: (1) making the skeleton of the physiotherapist proportional to the skeleton of the patient (*escalation*); and (2) translating the physiotherapist's skeleton to a new coordinate origin defined by the patient's waist (*translation*). Therefore, the monitoring based on joint coordinates becomes independent from the patient's size and location.

The escalation is the first transformation to be performed and it is responsible for eliminating any patient size dependence. To that end, the bodies of the physiotherapist and patient are compared in terms of bone length. It is important to calculate the escalation factor for each bone because some differences may appear according to the bones. When all the escalation factors are obtained, the next step is to compose the new target skeleton. The process starts from the hip centre to the final joints and generates a skeleton proportional to the original. The composition of the new skeleton consists of applying a specific formula to convert each joint. Whereas (x, y, z) represents the original coordinates and s the escalation factor, the formula is as follows:

$$\begin{cases} x' = x \cdot s_x \\ y' = y \cdot s_y \\ z' = z \cdot s_z \end{cases}$$

Once the escalation is completed, a skeleton proportional to the patient's one has been obtained. The next step is to translate the skeleton position to make the monitoring process independent of the patient location. As the desire is to move completely the new skeleton, we need to define a new coordinate origin from which we can calculate the translation factor. The selected origin is the patient's hip though it could be any other point. The new coordinates (x', y' and z') are obtained by knowing the translation factor for the three components of each skeleton point (t_x, t_y, t_z). Afterwards, we have to apply the following transformation:

$$\begin{cases} x' = x + t_x \\ y' = y + t_y \\ z' = z + t_z \end{cases}$$

The final result represents the new physiotherapist's skeleton. It can now be compared to the patient's one, hence this method has proved to be a good solution to the aforementioned problem when working with absolute coordinates.

3.3 Monitoring Based on Bone Coordinates

In this case, unlike the previous monitoring technique, the verifications are based on bones and not joints. The way to know if a bone is properly positioned consists of analysing the coordinates of the joints which are united by that bone. The coordinates are compared to obtain the position of the bone. That position can be represented as a vector (x, y, z) used to check if is equal to the corresponding bone in the postures designed by the physiotherapist. We consider a threshold represented by three values (x, y, z), one per each component that can be different.

The monitoring technique can be generalized to some bones. This allows the process to check complete extremities instead of verifying each bone that composes them. For example, if the position of the knee is not relevant, it is possible to check the patient's right leg taking into account only the right foot and the right point of the hip.

The necessary verifications for each posture have to be defined and created by code with the related thresholds. The main reason is the impossibility to define generic criteria for all the bones and extremities of the postures. For example, if a posture implies that the patient must raise an arm (in parallel to the floor), we only need to check the x and y coordinates of the shoulder because the z component has no influence. However, if the patient must raise the same arm although now clockwise, the components to be analysed are the z and y, which should match. Therefore, each posture implies the definition of its own verifications without being possible to define general rules.

3.4 Monitoring Based on Angles between Bones

The last monitoring option analysed has into account the angle generated by the corresponding joint through its bones. The verification consists of comparing the angle between each pair of bones in the patient with the correlative in the posture defined by the physiotherapist. The comparison considers a specific error threshold with the aim to allow some flexibility.

Figure 8. a) Angle of physiotherapist (α) and patient elbow (β); b) elbow checking through angles between bones

For instance, if the objective is to check an elbow, the process calculates the corresponding angle in the postures of the patient and the physiotherapist (previously defined as the expected one, see Figure 8-a). The joint will be in a correct position if the following formula is fulfilled:

$$\beta \in [\alpha - \gamma, \alpha + \gamma]$$

Figure 8-b shows an example in which the angle comparison is not successful, thus the patient is performing the posture in the wrong way.

4. DISCUSSION

The monitoring possibilities analysed in the previous sections have to be compared to select the most adequate. This step is essential in order to develop reliable and useful rehabilitation systems based on movement interaction.

The monitoring option based on the coordinates of bones does not take as a reference the coordinate origin offered by Kinect. This means that the verification process is independent of the patient location. Therefore, there is a high degree of flexibility to monitor movements. We only need to check a posture no matter where the user is. However, the generalization of checks for a specific posture is a complex task. The reason is that it not always requires the verification of the same coordinate components of the joint or even the same joints. In addition, it is not possible to establish a threshold of global error for a posture as it differs from one bone to another and between components of the same joint. Thus, the use of bone coordinates to monitor any posture in rehabilitation processes seems to be very complex. In short, this technique is not an adequate option to check non-predefined postures as it needs a manual definition, made by code, for each posture to be verified.

The monitoring option based on checking angles between joints provides a more generic solution. The main reason is that it allows the generation of the same threshold for all joints or one per joint. This is an important detail taking into account that the patient could present movement limitations. However, there are two main problems when using joint angles:

- The first and most important problem comes from the fact that the two angles compared, although matching, does not ensure that the implied bones are in the same position. The problem is that it does not check the position of final joints such as hands and feet. For instance, a person could create a 90° angle with their right elbow and the fingers of the right hand pointing to the left; at the same time, another person could maintain their fingers pointing upwards though keeping a 90° angle with their right elbow. Although both of them have the same angle, the postures are different. Therefore, this technique has to be combined with coordinates checking since the coincidence of angles is necessary, but not sufficient;
- An additional problem is the difficulty to verify some joints, such as the shoulders and the neck, whose rotation capability is significantly higher than others like the elbows and knees. When the joint offers only one movement, comparison is possible. However, if the joint has multiple movements, the comparison becomes an impossible process with devices such as Kinect due to the impossibility of obtaining the orientation of the angle.

The first analysed technique, based on joint coordinates or spheres, becomes important as it solves the problems found using angles and bones coordinates. As the angle-based monitoring, it can generalize thresholds by creating one or more for each posture. In addition, the spheres technique checks postures regardless of the joint and/or the bone because all the verifications have an identical behaviour. This solution has not been found in the other techniques.

The monitoring based on spheres solves another problem. The use of angles does not ensure the performance of a correct posture. The spheres technique checks if each joint (including the final extremities) has its coordinates within the corresponding sphere. This means that the technique eliminates the possibility to confuse one posture with another. Nevertheless, escalation and translation are required processes to complete the verification without problems. These additional transformations are not needed in the other monitoring options, however they allow a more reliable technique.

Therefore, the benefits offered by the technique based on joint coordinates have provided support in order to find an adequate process to monitor patient's postures. This technique has been incorporated into SIVIRE. With it, the system has the capacity to guide and correct patients during the rehabilitation therapy defined by the physiotherapists (see Figure 4). This capacity implies to monitor the patients regardless of their position when it is not needed. Therefore, the complete system, from the editor to the monitoring module, composes a useful tool to create any

rehabilitation process based on exercises composed of postures repetitions and transitions between them.

5. PRELIMINARY EVALUATION

In this section, we present the outcomes of the system evaluation performed with real users. We have focused on the assessment of the Quality in Use of the application taking as a reference the ISO/IEC 25062 [5]. We have also used the System Usability Scale (SUS) [1] to assess the users' satisfaction. The main goal of the evaluation was to test the software application developed to monitor and guide the patients using the monitoring technique based on joint coordinates. The method used in the evaluation is explained next.

5.1 Participants

We assessed the system with five users, which were not involved in any real rehabilitation process to focus the evaluation in the interaction with the application. This way, we could discard interaction problems related to the particular motor skills of the users. Table 1 shows the key characteristics and capabilities of the user group.

Table 1. Participants' characteristics

Participant	Age	Computer Experience	Product Experience	Rehabilitation Experience
1	20-25	2	1	2
2	20-25	2	1	1
3	20-30	3	1	1
4	20-30	3	3	3
5	30-35	3	2	3

Experience: 1, Low; 2, Medium; 3, High

5.2 Context of Product Use in the Test

We performed the assessment in a controlled setting using a rectangular-shaped room in the research lab simulating the conditions that a real patient would have at home, in the expected context of use. Figure 9 shows the setting and type of space in which the evaluation was conducted. The Kinect device was on a one-meter-high table. The tester was in the room supervising the actions of the user and writing down possible problems or incidents.

Figure 9. Setting and space used for the evaluation

We used a laptop with Windows 8.1 and Kinect for Windows SDK 2.0. The laptop was equipped with 4GB of RAM and an Intel Core i5 processor at 2.40 GHz, and a USB 3.0 port to connect the Microsoft Kinect 2.0 device.

The participants had to performed two concrete tasks that were described in detail in a sheet we handed them out at the beginning of the evaluation. Any of the tasks had a predefined time limit to complete. The first task was navigating throughout the application and the second was to carry out a set of rehabilitation exercises. These two tasks were considered essential as they were the most frequent tasks any user should be able to do.

5.3 Usability Metrics

We measured the system usability by three types of metrics: effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction, i.e., the users' subjective reactions to using the system.

Effectiveness was measured by considering the percent task completion, frequency of errors and frequency of assistance offered to the participant from the testers. These measures are shown in Table 2 and Table 3 in the columns named "Assisted Completion Rate", "Unassisted Completion Rate", "Errors" and "Request for assistance".

Efficiency was measured by calculating the time needed to complete a task (mm:ss). Specifically, the mean time taken to achieve the task. These measures are shown in Table 2 and Table 3 in the column named "Task Time".

Finally, satisfaction was measured with the System Usability Scale (SUS) [1]. This questionnaire is composed of ten statements related to the system usage and the user had to indicate the degree of agreement or disagreement on a 5-point scale.

5.4 Results

5.4.1 Data Analysis

The way we treated data during the evaluation is described as follows:

- Data Collection: The behaviour of the users was classified considering failures, successes and requests for assistance. An error was considered when the user performed an action that did not drive to the completion of the task. In addition, we considered a help request whenever the user asked for help;
- Data reduction: Each task was analysed independently. The data were split into two groups according to the level of experience with the application (With experience and without previous experience);
- Statistical Analysis: We have used the mean and the maximum and minimum values as statistical measures.

5.4.2 Presentation of Results

Next, we present the measures of effectiveness and efficiency that characterize the performance results per each one of the tasks. Table 2 presents in a tabular form the performance results of Task 1 whereas Figure 10 presents the results in a graphical way.

Table 2. Performance results of Task 1: Navigation throughout the application

Participants	Assisted Completion Rate	Unassisted Completion Rate	Task Time (min)	Errors	Requests for assistance
1	12.5	87.5	01:10	0	1
2	37.5	62.5	02:13	1	3
3	25	75	01:39	0	2
4	0	100	00:40	0	0
5	12.5	87.5	01:35	0	1
With experience	6.25	93.75	01:07	0	0.5
Without experience	25	75	01:40	0.33	2
Media	17.5	82.5	1:27	0.2	1.4
Min.	0	62.5	00:40	0	0
Max.	37.5	100	02:13	1	3

Figure 10. Graphical representation of the results of performance of Task 1: navigation throughout the application

Table 3 shows the performance results of Task 2 and Figure 11 presents the same results in a graphical way.

Table 3. Performance results of Task 2: Carrying out the rehabilitation exercises

Participants	Assisted Completion Rate	Unassisted Completion Rate	Task Time (min)	Errors	Requests for assistance
1	25	75	02:30	0	1
2	50	50	03:35	0	2
3	25	75	02:25	0	2
4	0	100	02:10	0	0
5	25	75	03:10	0	3
<i>With experience</i>	12.5	87.5	02:40	0	1.5
<i>Without experience</i>	33.33	66.67	02:50	0	1.67
<i>Media</i>	25	75	2:46	0	1.6
<i>Min.</i>	0	50	2:10	0	0
<i>Max.</i>	50	100	3:35	0	3

Figure 11. Graphical representation of the results of performance of Task 2: navigation throughout the application

5.4.3 Satisfaction Results

At the end of the sessions, the five participants completed the questionnaire proposed by the System Usability Scale (SUS) [1].

Table 4 shows the results of the SUS scores per participant. The final value is between 0 and 100, being 100 the highest degree of user's satisfaction. With a mean score of 85.8 we can conclude that satisfaction was quite high.

Table 4. Satisfaction Results per participant

Participant	SUS Score
1	87.5
2	75
3	90
4	87.5
5	80
<i>Mean</i>	85,8

6. CONCLUSIONS

Healthcare environments are undergoing important changes thanks to current technology. Movement-based interaction is a significant step forward as it facilitates the monitoring of exercises based on posture repetitions. As a consequence, this type of interaction improves the process of checking therapies consisting of constant repetitions of postures with a correct verification and guidance of the patient. In this context, the authors have developed SIVIRE which could be defined as a comprehensive tool focused on editing, monitoring and guiding exercises for physical rehabilitation.

The system supports medical staff with a virtual editor to create exercises. They can interact with the editor manually or through movement-based interaction. The defined exercises generate rehabilitation tables that will be received by the patients in the desktop application that is part of the system. In this case, SIVIRE avoids the need for a patient to move from their home environment to the rehabilitation centre. In addition, the tool gathers statistics about the progress what is a useful element for medical staff to control the therapies. Together with these features, the system provides two main contributions regarding existing related works. Firstly, the system has the capacity to adapt the exercises to the patient's conditions. And secondly, we can adapt the complexity and difficulty of the exercises according to the patient's evolution throughout the rehabilitation process.

The development of the system posed a number of challenges we had to tackle. This paper is focused on a specific one: the monitoring process of the patient while performing the exercises. The selection of the adequate process is essential to gain accuracy when verifying the correctness of postures. Therefore, we have presented the analysis of three different monitoring mechanisms. Each one of them works under different considerations: joint coordinates, bone coordinates and the angle between bones. The study reveals that monitoring based on joint coordinates is the most adequate, and we have incorporated it in the development of SIVIRE. This technique can generalize thresholds and verifies postures regardless of the analysed joint or bone. In addition, this technique does not allow the system to confuse two different postures. Finally, the outcomes of the system evaluation prove that SIVIRE offers a reliable and useful tool to support rehabilitation therapies, both for patients and physiotherapists.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work has been partially funded by project with reference UCTR150497 from the Castilla-La Mancha Regional Government: Junta de Comunidades de Castilla-La Mancha, Consejería de Empleo y Economía. We would also like to thank Tecon Solutions Informática S.L. for their collaboration on this application.

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